

MODERN POSSIBILITIES OF DIAGNOSTICS AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF STRICTURES AND OTHER DISEASES OF THE URETHRA

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ABSTRACT

Urethral diseases, including urethral strictures, post-traumatic injuries, and inflammatory lesions, represent a significant part of urological pathology and often result in severe lower urinary tract dysfunction and reduced quality of life. Recent advances in reconstructive urology and endoscopic technologies have considerably expanded the diagnostic and therapeutic options for these patients. The aim of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of modern diagnostic and surgical treatment methods for urethral diseases based on clinical, functional, and urodynamic outcomes. A total of 130 patients with various forms of urethral pathology were examined and treated. The diagnostic protocol included uroflowmetry, urethrography, ultrasonography, and endoscopic assessment. The results demonstrated that modern reconstructive procedures and minimally invasive endoscopic interventions significantly improved urodynamic parameters, reduced recurrence rates, and enhanced patients' quality of life.

Relevance. Urethral diseases, particularly urethral strictures, remain one of the most pressing problems in modern urology. According to the literature, urethral strictures occur in 0.6–1.4% of the male population and are one of the leading causes of bladder outlet obstruction and chronic urinary disorders. The main etiologic factors include traumatic injuries, inflammatory processes, iatrogenic interventions, and congenital urethral malformations.

Despite the widespread use of endoscopic treatments, the problem of disease recurrence remains a pressing issue. In recent years, significant progress has been achieved thanks to the introduction of reconstructive surgeries using buccal grafts, modern laser technologies, and improved endoscopic techniques. These approaches allow for the permanent restoration of urethral patency, improved urodynamic parameters, and an enhanced quality of life for patients. In this regard, the assessment of the effectiveness of modern methods of diagnosis and surgical treatment of urethral diseases is of significant scientific and practical interest for improving urological care.

Purpose of the study. To evaluate the clinical effectiveness of modern methods of diagnosis and surgical treatment of urethral diseases based on the analysis of urodynamic parameters, recurrence rate and quality of life of patients.

Materials and research methods. The study was carried out at a specialized urological center in the period from 2021 to 2024. The study included 130 patients aged 21 to 74 years with various forms of urethral pathology. The average age of the subjects was 48.6 ± 2.3 years. All patients gave informed consent to participate in the study and conduct diagnostic and therapeutic measures.

Among those examined, urethral strictures were the most frequently diagnosed – in 82 (63.1%) patients. Post-traumatic urethral injuries were detected in 18 (13.8%) patients, inflammatory strictures – in 21 (16.2%), congenital malformations of the urethra – in 9 (6.9%) patients.

To compare the effectiveness of various treatment methods, patients were divided into two groups. The first group included 68 patients who underwent minimally invasive procedures, including internal optical urethrotomy, laser urethrotomy, and endoscopic urethral dilation. The second group included 62 patients who underwent reconstructive surgeries: anastomotic urethroplasty, buccal substitution urethroplasty, and combined reconstructive procedures.

The diagnostic process included a patient history and complaint collection, a physical examination, blood and urine laboratory tests, urinary tract ultrasound, retrograde urethrography, urethrocystoscopy, and uroflowmetry. The International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS) was used to assess the severity of lower urinary tract symptoms, and patients' quality of life was assessed using the Quality of Life (QoL) scale.

Treatment efficacy was assessed at 3, 6, and 12 months after surgery. The primary outcome measures were maximum urinary flow rate (Q_{max}), residual urine volume, symptom severity according to the IPSS scale, quality of life indicators, and disease recurrence rate.

Statistical data processing was performed using the SPSS Statistics 23.0 software package. For quantitative indicators, mean values and standard errors of the mean ($M \pm m$) were calculated. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to determine relationships between the parameters under study. Differences were considered statistically significant at a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion. An analysis of treatment results revealed positive dynamics in clinical and functional indicators in the majority of patients in both groups. Improved urination, reduced obstructive symptoms, and improved quality of life were noted already in the early postoperative period.

Before treatment, the average maximum urine flow rate (Q_{max}) was 7.2 ± 0.4 ml/s, indicating significant urodynamic impairment. After treatment, this indicator increased to 18.9 ± 0.7 ml/s ($p < 0.001$), indicating significant restoration of urethral patency.

The average residual urine volume before treatment was 86.4 ± 5.2 ml. After surgical correction, it decreased to 24.1 ± 2.8 ml ($p < 0.001$), indicating restoration of full bladder emptying.

The severity of lower urinary tract symptoms according to the IPSS scale decreased from 22.7 ± 1.1 to 8.3 ± 0.6 points ($p < 0.001$). At the same time, a significant improvement in the

patients' quality of life was noted: the QoL indicator decreased from 5.1 ± 0.2 to 1.8 ± 0.1 points ($p < 0.001$).

A comparative analysis of treatment outcomes showed that minimally invasive methods were less traumatic, resulted in shorter hospital stays, and resulted in faster patient recovery. However, for extended, complex, and recurrent strictures, better long-term results were achieved after reconstructive surgeries.

The recurrence rate in the overall observation group decreased from $34.6 \pm 2.4\%$ to $9.2 \pm 1.3\%$ ($p < 0.001$). The lowest recurrence rates were observed after substitution buccal urethroplasty and anastomotic reconstruction of the urethra.

The obtained data indicate a significant restoration of urodynamics and improvement in the quality of life of patients (Table 1).

Table 1

Main clinical and functional indicators of patients before and after treatment (M±m)

Indicator	Before treatment	After treatment	p
Maximum urine flow rate (Qmax), ml/s	$7,2 \pm 0,4$	$18,9 \pm 0,7$	$<0,001$
Residual urine, ml	$86,4 \pm 5,2$	$24,1 \pm 2,8$	$<0,001$
IPSS scores	$22,7 \pm 1,1$	$8,3 \pm 0,6$	$<0,001$
Quality of Life Index (QoL)	$5,1 \pm 0,2$	$1,8 \pm 0,1$	$<0,001$
Recurrence rate, %	$34,6 \pm 2,4$	$9,2 \pm 1,3$	$<0,001$

Correlation analysis revealed a statistically significant positive relationship between stricture length and the likelihood of disease recurrence ($r=0.74$; $p < 0.001$). A strong positive correlation was also established between an increase in maximum urinary flow rate and an improvement in patients' quality of life ($r=0.69$; $p < 0.001$). A moderate positive correlation was found between residual urine volume and the severity of symptoms according to the IPSS scale ($r=0.66$; $p < 0.001$). A strong positive correlation was found between stricture length and the likelihood of disease recurrence.

We found a moderate correlation between patient age and the duration of postoperative rehabilitation ($r=0.48$; $p < 0.05$). A negative correlation between reconstructive surgery and the recurrence rate ($r=-0.72$; $p < 0.001$) indicates the high effectiveness of reconstructive surgery in the long term.

Thus, the results of the study confirm that the use of modern reconstructive and minimally invasive technologies provides a significant improvement in urodynamic parameters, a reduction in the frequency of relapses and an increase in the quality of life of patients with urethral diseases. The most stable long-term results are achieved when using reconstructive treatment methods in patients with complex and extensive lesions of the urethra. The study confirms the high effectiveness of modern reconstructive and minimally invasive technologies for the treatment of urethral diseases.

Endoscopic methods offer several advantages, including low invasiveness, a short postoperative period, and rapid patient recovery. However, for extended and recurrent

strictures, the effectiveness of reconstructive urethroplasty remains significantly higher. Of particular interest is the use of buccal mucosa as a grafting material, which ensures high graft survival and a low rate of urethral re-stenosis.

These results are consistent with current international guidelines from the European Association of Urology and support the need for individualized treatment selection based on the clinical situation.

Conclusions:

1. Modern minimally invasive and reconstructive techniques are effective treatments for urethral diseases;
2. After treatment, significant improvements in urodynamic parameters and quality of life are observed in patients;
3. Reconstructive urethroplasty demonstrates the best long-term results for extended and recurrent urethral strictures;
4. Maximum urinary flow rate after treatment increases more than 2.5-fold ($p < 0.001$);
5. The recurrence rate after using modern reconstructive technologies is significantly lower compared to traditional treatment methods;
6. An individualized approach to surgical selection improves treatment effectiveness and reduces the risk of complications..

References:

- 1.Kulkarni S., Joshi P., Surana S. Management of Urethral Strictures. Indian Journal of Urology. 2023;39(2):101–110.
- 2.Mundy A.R., Andrich D.E. Urethral Strictures. BJU International. 2022;130(4):395–406.
- 3.Пушкаръ Д.Ю., Аполихин О.И. Реконструктивная урология. – М.: Практическая медицина, 2022. – 548 с.
- 4.Аляев Ю.Г., Глыбочко П.В. Урология. – М.: ГЭОТАР-Медиа, 2023. 768 с.
- 5.Barbagli G., Lazzeri M. Contemporary Urethral Reconstruction. European Urology. 2023;84(2):172–184.
- 6.Chapple C.R., Andrich D.E. Guidelines on Urethral Stricture Disease. European Association of Urology Guidelines. 2024;1–42.
- 7.Meeks J.J., Erickson B.A. Male Urethral Reconstruction. Urologic Clinics of North America. 2023;50(1):37–49.